

Synthesis, characterisation and antimycobacterial screening of 5(4*H*)-oxazolone derivatives against *M. tuberculosis* H37Rv

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Abstract : In search of new antitubercular agents, a new series of 4-(substituted benzylidene)-2-*p*-tolylloxazol-5(4*H*)-ones (5a-h) has been designed, synthesized and subjected to evaluate their antimycobacterial activity against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* H37Rv in comparison with standard drugs Rifampicin and Isoniazid. The out-put of these studies disclosed that all the synthesized target molecules of the series displayed good to moderate activity with MIC values ranging 8–64 µg/mL. Compound 5e having three methoxy groups, is the most distinctive compound identified, amongst the series because of its remarkable *in vitro* antimycobacterial activity and thus may act as a promising lead molecule for further explorations.

Keywords : 5-Oxazolones, Erlenmeyer-Plochl synthesis, antimycobacterial, Rifampicin, Isoniazide.

Introduction

Highly contagious, air-borne dreadful disease ‘Tuberculosis’ (TB) is caused by *Micobacterium tuberculosis* and has evolved with tough resistance to many drugs formulated and thus proved to be fatal causing more human deaths^{1,2}. Over the past few decades no novel potential drugs have been discovered to counter back this notorious disease^{3,4}. Therefore, there is an essential necessitate to desperately design and synthesise new drugs against TB.

For this reason, we have thrown our attention on potent heterocyclic moiety i.e. 5(4*H*)-oxazolones with a wide spectrum of pharmacological properties such as antimicrobial⁵, analgesic⁶, anti-inflammatory⁷, muscle relaxant⁸, neuroleptic⁹, anticancer¹⁰, antagonistic¹¹, antiangiogenic¹², immunomodulator¹³, cardiotoxic¹⁴, cyclooxygenase2inhibitors¹⁵ and tyrosinase inhibitor¹⁶ etc. These molecules are considered as internal anhydrides of acyl amino acids and form an important class of five membered heterocyclic compounds¹⁷. These are also act as intermediates for several important organic molecules such as amino acids, peptides¹⁸, heterocyclic presursors¹⁹ for biosensors coupling, and photosensitive composition devices for proteins²⁰.

Even so, this class of molecules remained unutilized for antituberculosis activity. In consideration, a series of eight 4-(substituted benzylidene)-2-*p*-tolylloxazol-5(4*H*)-ones (5a-h) has been synthesized, characterized and evaluated for their efficiency as antimycobacterial agents against *M. tuberculosis* H37Rv in comparison to the two most powerful first-line tuberculosis drugs Rifampicin (RIF) and Isoniazid (INH).

Results and discussion

Chemistry :

The present study reports the synthesis, characterization and antimycobacterial activity of the novel 5(4*H*)-oxazolones. The title compounds have been synthesized from commercially available compound *p*-toullic acid (1). It was converted to *p*-toullic acid chloride (2) using thionylchloride and dichloro methane (DCM). The acid chloride (2) obtained was immediately treated *in situ* with glycine (amino acetic acid) in sodium hydroxide to yield 2-(4-methyl benzamido) acetic acid (3), which on further reaction with various *p*-substituted benzaldehydes (4a-h) in presence of sodium acetate, acetic anhydride and freshly activated 4 Å molecular sieves yielded the target molecules (5a-h) in high yields. The use of 4 Å molecular

sieves in the reaction, enhanced the reaction rates by the way of affecting cyclodehydration, thus increase in the yield of the products. The crude 4-(substituted benzylidene)-2-*p*-tolylloxazol-5(4*H*)-ones (**5a-h**) obtained via Erlenmeyer-Plochl azlactone synthesis, on recrystallization yielded yellow crystalline solids. The structures of the target molecules are confirmed on the basis of physical and spectral data viz. FT-IR, FT-¹H NMR, FT-¹³C NMR, mass spectroscopy and elemental analyses. All the synthesized compounds were in conformity with the structures envisaged. The steps involved in the synthesis are given in Scheme 1.

Pharmacological evaluation :

All the synthesized 5(4*H*)-oxazolones (**5a-h**) have been evaluated for their antimycobacterial activity and the obtained results are summarized in Table 1. All the compounds (**5a-h**) were screened primarily against *M. tuberculosis* H37Rv at a single concentration of 100 µg/ml adopting broth macrodilution assay. The potent compounds from the results of this initial screening were picked up and further tested for minimum inhibitory concentration

(MIC) values at much lower concentrations, by serial dilution against *M. tuberculosis* H37Rv, using nitrate reductase assay (NRA)²¹. By addition of the NRA reagent, a change in colour to pink is observed indicating the growth of the microorganism in the microtitre plate. Thus, it is evident that MIC, the lowest concentration values of the compounds exhibits, no colour change relative to controls used for the study. Each evaluation was performed in duplicate, in two separate set of experiments and the average value is taken. Solvent, dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO) is used as negative control and used to make two fold dilutions of test compounds (**5a-h**). The standard reference drugs used to compare the potency of the title compounds were Rifampicin and Isoniazid. All the newly synthesized 5(4*H*)-oxazolones (**5a-h**) exhibited remarkable antituberculosis activities in comparison with the reference drugs.

From Table 1, it has been observed that all the 5-oxazolone derivatives have shown notable antimycobacterial activity with MIC values ranging from 8–64 µg/mL against *M. tuberculosis* H37Rv. Among the eight title

Scheme 1. Synthetic route of 4-(substituted benzylidene)-2-*p*-tolylloxazol-5(4*H*)-ones (**5a-h**).

Table 1. The minimum inhibitory concentrations (MIC)^a of 4-(substituted benzylidene)-2-*p*-tolylloxazol-5(4*H*)-ones (**5a-h**) against *M. tuberculosis* H37Rv

Compd.	-R group	MIC (µg/ml)
5a	H	16
5b	4-CH ₃	16
5c	4-OCH ₃	16
5d	2,5-OCH ₃	16
5e	2,4,6-OCH ₃	08
5f	4-Cl	32
5g	4-Br	64
5h	4-NO ₂	64
Rifampicin		02
Isoniazide		02

^aResults are from one experiment of at least two independent repeats.

compounds studied, compound **5e** having 2,4,6-trimethoxy group exhibited potent *in vitro* antimycobacterial activity with MIC value of 8 µg/mL. Compounds **5b**, **5c**, **5d** with 4-methyl, 4-methoxy, 2,5-dimethoxy substituents respectively, exhibited equivalent activity to that of the unsubstituted parent compound i.e. 4-benzylidene-2-*p*-tolylloxazol-5(4*H*)-one (**5a**). From the above study, it is clearly evident that the electron withdrawing substituent (4-chloro, 4-bromo, 4-nitro groups) on the benzene ring of compounds **5f**, **5g** and **5h** respectively showed moderate activity against tested organism *M. tuberculosis* H37Rv. Amongst the electron withdrawing substituted compounds (**5f-h**), chloro substituent (**5f**) is considered as better inhibitor than bromo and nitro groups in the series. On the whole, compound **5e** exhibited prominent *in vitro* antimycobacterial activity against *M. tuberculosis* H37Rv with MIC value 8 µg/mL.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of synthetic grade and commercially procured from Qualigens. All the organic solvents adopted in the study were commercially available and dried using standard procedures. Melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. IR spectra were obtained on Perkin-Elmer 1330 infrared spectrophotometer using KBr disc method. ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR were recorded by "Mercury-400" spectrometer using deuteriated dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO) and deuteriated chloroform (CDCl₃) as solvents. The

chemical shift values δ are expressed in ppm. Elemental analyses were performed on Elementar Vario EL elemental analyzer. To assess the progress of reaction, thin layer chromatography (TLC) were performed by pre coated silica gel plates (G 350, Merck) and the compounds were visualized with aqueous KMnO₄. The title compounds (**5a-h**) were recrystallized twice from hot benzene to enhance the degree of purity for the pharmacological studies.

Synthesis of *p*-toullic acid chloride (**2**) :

A mixture of *p*-toullic acid (**1**) (0.1 mol) in DCM (30 mL) was added slowly to thionyl chloride (0.3 mol) and the reaction mixture was heated to reflux for 4 h under anhydrous conditions. The excess thionyl chloride was distilled off under reduced pressure and the resultant acid chloride (**2**) was used *in situ* for further reaction with glycine.

Synthesis of 2-(4-methylbenzamido)acetic acid (**3**) :

Glycine (0.1 mol) was dissolved in NaOH (30 mL, 2 *N*) and stirred vigorously with mechanical stirrer, until it is totally dissolved. This was added dropwise to the crude acid chloride (**2**) (0.1 mol) and stirred vigorously for 1 h. Later it was poured into crushed ice and acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid with stirring. The obtained crude compound (**3**) was washed with cold water, dried and recrystallized from boiling water.

White powder, yield : 75%, m.p. 205 °C, IR (KBr, ν_{\max} , cm⁻¹) : 794, 1187, 1443, 1664, 1754; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO, δ ppm) : 2.75 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.72 (2H, s, CH₂), 7.33 (2H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz, Ar-H), 7.45 (2H, d, *J* 8.8 Hz, Ar-H), 8.15 (1H, s, NH), 12.66 (1H, br s, COOH); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO, δ ppm) : 22.8, 41.1, 127.6, 128.6, 132.4, 134.8, 170.5, 171.2; ESI-MS (*m/z*) : 193 (M⁺). Anal. Calcd. for C₁₀H₁₁NO₃ : C, 62.17, H, 5.74; N, 7.25; O, 24.84. Found : C, 62.15; H, 5.76; N, 7.21%.

Synthesis of 4-(substituted benzylidene)-2-*p*-tolylloxazol-5(4*H*)-ones (**5a-h**) :

A mixture of dry 2-(4-methylbenzamido)acetic acid (**3**) (0.01 mol), substituted aromatic aldehyde (**4a-h**) (0.01 mol), powdered anhydrous sodium acetate (0.01 mol) and high-grade acetic anhydride (0.03 mol) was heated at 110 °C with constant shaking. Then 4 Å molecular sieves

(2 g) were added to the reaction mixture and heated on a water bath for 1 h with occasional stirring. After completion of the reaction, the molecular sieves were removed by filtration and ethanol (10 mL) was added slowly to the reaction mixture and left overnight at room temperature. The crystalline product thus obtained was filtered, washed successively with alcohol followed by water and dried. The obtained 5-oxazolones (**5a-h**) were recrystallized from hot benzene.

4-Benzylidene-2-p-tolyloxazol-5(4H)-one (5a) :

Yellow crystals, yield : 78%, m.p. 187 °C; IR (KBr, ν_{\max} , cm^{-1}) : 934, 1134, 1476, 1657; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ ppm) : 2.90 (3H, s, CH_3), 7.11 (1H, s, CH), 7.28 (2H, d, J 8.8 Hz, Ar-H), 7.39 (2H, d, J 8.8 Hz, Ar-H), 7.53 (3H, m, Ar-H), 7.61 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz, Ar-H); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ ppm) : 23.1, 110.6, 121.4, 121.6, 122.4, 122.9, 127.2, 128.7, 129.1, 133.4, 134.9, 141.6, 166.0, 174.9; ESI-MS (m/z) : 263 (M^+). Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{13}\text{NO}_2$: C, 77.55; H, 4.98; N, 5.32; O, 12.15. Found : C, 77.50; H, 4.59; N, 5.30%.

4-(4-Methyl benzylidene)-2-p-tolyloxazol-5(4H)-one (5b) :

Pale yellow crystals, yield : 80%, m.p. 173 °C; IR (KBr, ν_{\max} , cm^{-1}) : 956, 1128, 1455, 1623; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ ppm) : 2.85 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.89 (3H, s, CH_3), 7.20 (1H, s, CH), 7.24 (2H, d, J 8.8 Hz, Ar-H), 7.35 (2H, d, J 8.8 Hz, Ar-H), 7.44 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz, Ar-H), 7.51 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz, Ar-H); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ ppm) : 21.9, 23.7, 112.3, 128.0, 129.5, 131.2, 132.5, 135.8, 143.2, 166.7, 174.1; ESI-MS (m/z) : 277 (M^+). Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{15}\text{NO}_2$: C, 77.96; H, 5.45; N, 5.05; O, 11.54. Found : C, 77.90; H, 5.43; N, 5.01%.

4-(4-Methoxy benzylidene)-2-p-tolyloxazol-5(4H)-one (5c) :

Yellow crystals, yield : 82%, m.p. 166 °C; IR (KBr, ν_{\max} , cm^{-1}) : 934, 1134, 1476, 1657, 1765, 1834; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ ppm) : 2.81 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.54 (3H, s, OCH_3), 7.09 (1H, s, CH), 7.18 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz, Ar-H), 7.21 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz, Ar-H), 7.32 (2H, d, J 8.8 Hz, Ar-H), 7.39 (2H, d, J 8.8 Hz, Ar-H); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ ppm) : 23.0, 55.5, 110.5, 126.4, 128.0, 131.1, 132.1, 134.6, 142.2, 158.1, 166.8,

173.8; ESI-MS (m/z) : 293 (M^+). Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{15}\text{NO}_3$: C, 73.71; H, 5.15; N, 4.78; O, 16.36. Found : C, 73.73; H, 5.18; N, 4.75%.

4-(2,5-Dimethoxy benzylidene)-2-p-tolyloxazol-5(4H)-one (5d) :

Bright yellow crystals, yield : 79%, m.p. 163 °C; IR (KBr, ν_{\max} , cm^{-1}) : 919, 1146, 1256, 1388, 1443, 1665; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ ppm) : 2.88 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.51 (3H, s, OCH_3), 3.56 (3H, s, OCH_3), 7.15 (1H, s, CH), 7.22 (1H, s, Ar-H), 7.28–7.33 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.38 (2H, d, J 9.2 Hz, Ar-H), 7.41 (2H, d, J 8.8 Hz, Ar-H); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ ppm) : 23.1, 54.5, 58.2, 109.7, 120.9, 122.3, 124.4, 127.9, 132.1, 136.5, 143.1, 154.5, 158.2, 166.4, 172.6; ESI-MS (m/z) : 323 (M^+). Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}_4$: C, 70.58; H, 5.30; N, 4.33; O, 19.79. Found : C, 70.54; H, 5.28; N, 4.30%.

4-(2,4,6-Trimethoxy benzylidene)-2-p-tolyloxazol-5(4H)-one (5e) :

Deep yellow crystals, yield : 84%, m.p. 171 °C; IR (KBr, ν_{\max} , cm^{-1}) : 957, 1155, 1261, 1452, 1666, 1786, 1811; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ ppm) : 2.83 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.53 (3H, s, OCH_3), 3.55 (3H, s, OCH_3), 3.58 (3H, s, OCH_3), 7.16 (1H, s, CH), 7.21 (1H, s, Ar-H), 7.23 (1H, s, Ar-H), 7.28 (1H, s, Ar-H), 7.33 (2H, d, J 8.8 Hz, Ar-H), 7.38 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz, Ar-H); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ ppm) : 23.7, 56.2, 60.9, 62.0, 107.6, 120.6, 126.2, 127.9, 129.6, 130.9, 135.0, 141.0, 154.7, 156.8, 158.0, 166.8, 173.8; ESI-MS (m/z) : 353 (M^+). Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{19}\text{NO}_5$: C, 67.98; H, 5.42; N, 3.96; O, 22.64. Found : C, 67.99; H, 5.40; N, 3.97%.

4-(4-Chloro benzylidene)-2-p-tolyloxazol-5(4H)-one (5f) :

Yellow crystals, yield : 78%, m.p. 179 °C; IR (KBr, ν_{\max} , cm^{-1}) : 781, 962, 1166, 1424, 1662, 1788; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ ppm) : 2.95 (3H, s, CH_3), 7.19 (1H, s, CH), 7.28 (2H, d, J 8.8 Hz, Ar-H), 7.32 (2H, d, J 9.2 Hz, Ar-H), 7.42 (2H, d, J 8.8 Hz, Ar-H), 7.46 (2H, d, J 8.8 Hz, Ar-H); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ ppm) : 23.8, 114.5, 128.0, 128.9, 130.2, 131.2, 131.7, 133.4, 135.8, 137.3, 143.2, 166.2, 174.5; ESI-MS (m/z) : 297 (M^+), 299 ($\text{M}+2$). Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{12}\text{ClNO}_2$: C, 68.58; H, 4.06; Cl, 11.91; N, 4.70; O, 10.75. Found : C, 68.55; H, 4.02; N, 4.68%.

4-(4-Bromo benzylidene)-2-p-tolyloxazol-5(4H)-one (5g) :

Pale yellow crystals, yield : 70%, m.p. 181 °C; IR (KBr, ν_{\max} , cm^{-1}) : 956, 1159, 1480, 1661; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ ppm) : 2.93 (3H, s, CH_3), 7.18 (1H, s, CH), 7.28 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz, Ar-H), 7.35 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz, Ar-H), 7.43–7.55 (4H, m, Ar-H); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ ppm) : 23.6, 113.8, 125.5, 127.0, 128.8, 129.8, 131.9, 132.1, 132.5, 133.1, 146.7, 165.8, 175.4; ESI-MS (m/z) : 341 (M^+). Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{12}\text{BrNO}_2$: C, 59.67; H, 3.53; Br, 23.35; N, 4.09; O, 9.35. Found : C, 59.66; H, 3.55; N, 4.04%.

4-(4-Nitro benzylidene)-2-p-tolyloxazol-5(4H)-one (5h) :

Bright yellow crystals, yield : 72%, m.p. 188 °C; IR (KBr, ν_{\max} , cm^{-1}) : 959, 1154, 1498, 1671; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ ppm) : 2.91 (3H, s, CH_3), 7.13 (1H, s, CH), 7.27 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz, Ar-H), 7.34 (2H, d, J 8.8 Hz, Ar-H), 7.59–7.65 (4H, m, Ar-H); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ ppm) : 23.4, 115.3, 123.6, 128.1, 131.4, 132.6, 134.5, 135.8, 139.1, 148.1, 165.5, 175.3; ESI-MS (m/z) : 308 (M^+). Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4$: C, 66.23; H, 3.92; N, 9.09; O, 20.76. Found : C, 66.20; H, 3.90; N, 9.04%.

Conclusion

In conclusion, a new series of 5(4H)-oxazolone derivatives were synthesized, fully characterised and assessed for their efficacy as antimycobacterial agents. The newly synthesized compounds exhibited potent activity against *M. tuberculosis* H37Rv. Compound **5e** possessing strong electron donating methoxy groups was found to be prominent *in vitro* antimycobacterial agent among the series studied. The results are promising and further investigations are in progress to improve their structure activity relationship (SAR).

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